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Hydrogenation of Si/SiO₂ interface using HF-etched wafer as a source of hydrogen

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E-mail: pakkiabh@fel.cvut.cz**Keywords:** silicon solar cell, surface passivation, hydrogenation, carrier lifetime, SiO₂, tunnel oxide

Abstract

Surface passivation plays an important role in solar cell efficiency, and a well-established surface passivation technique is using the silicon oxide layer. The ultrathin layer of so-called tunnel oxide is a core of very promising TOPCon technology. As a part of the technology, is a post-hydrogenation process that has been extensively developed and is utilized to mitigate the dangling bonds and other surface impurities mainly at the interface between silicon and oxide layer. Even though these commercial processes are very effective in terms of enhancing the silicon solar cell performance, they require extra layer deposition, firing step followed by layer removal. This work introduces the sandwiching process, a tunnel oxide hydrogenation approach in which a Si wafer bearing a chemical tunnel oxide is positioned between HF-etched wafers serving as hydrogen sources and subjected to a 650 °C anneal for 15 min. This process leads to achieving the effective carrier lifetimes of 0.1 ms. We have varied temperature conditions from 450 °C–850 °C to investigate the trade-off between the hydrogenation process and thermal oxidation that is a competing process. At 650 °C, we successfully maintained the desired oxide thickness between 1 nm and 2 nm along with a reliable carrier lifetime (~100 μs), exhibiting an error variation of ±5%. Although the measured carrier lifetime decreases by nearly 50% from its initial value i.e. ~100 μs, it exhibits relative temporal stability over a duration of up to 250 min. FTIR surface analysis of the sandwiched wafer confirms that the sandwiching process introduces additional hydrogen into the SiO₂ layer at the Si/SiO₂ interface.

Introduction

Silicon is by far the dominant semiconductor material in the photovoltaic industry, mostly due to its abundant availability, chemical stability, high technological maturity, and consequently high conversion efficiency [1–7]. A well-known advantage of silicon is that its native oxide can serve as a very effective surface passivation layer, providing excellent electrical and chemical stability. However, to comply with specific passivation and carrier transport requirement on the Si/SiO₂ interface, there are extremely high demands on the suppression of interfacial recombination defects. These defects are mainly crystallographic defects and unsaturated dangling bonds, as described schematically in figure 1. Over the past few decades, extensive research has focused on interface engineering strategies aimed at mitigating these recombination pathways, particularly through chemical passivation of the Si/SiO₂ interface.

Hydrogenation is a well-known technique widely used in silicon solar cell technology to passivate interfacial defects [8–11]. For decades, several investigations on high-temperature processes, including hydrogen-containing dielectric layers deposition, its thickness variation and post-metallization firing process which are used to passivate the Si/SiO₂ interface has been conducted [12–15]. Tunnel oxide passivated contact (TOPCon) technology has emerged as a top choice for high-efficiency silicon solar cells. It uses an ultrathin SiO_x tunnel oxide layer along with a heavily doped poly-Si layer. This combination provides excellent surface passivation and carrier selectivity [16–18]. Recent reports show that TOPCon solar cells have achieved certified champion

efficiencies exceeding 26%, while commercial mass-production TOPCon cells have reached $\geq 25\%$ efficiency [19–23]. However, the quality of the tunnel oxide passivation can suffer during high-temperature firing. This degradation mainly results from hydrogen diffusion and thermal stress. Introducing Al₂O₃ can help as a barrier against hydrogen [24]. Optimizing the thickness of the poly-Si and tunnel oxide layers, along with post-deposition annealing, is vital for reducing interface defects. This optimization also helps maximize implied open-circuit voltage and carrier lifetime [18, 25]. Ongoing research into the mechanisms of degradation and passivation strategies is crucial for the industrial-scale use and reliability of TOPCon solar cells [17, 24].

Yablonovitch *et al* found that a common treatment for silicon surfaces, which involves oxidation followed by hydrofluoric acid (HF) etching, have achieved $\tau_{\text{eff}} = 22\text{--}35$ ms for a 250 μm thick (1 1 1) oriented wafer from a 150 Ωcm (probably n-type) float-zone (FZ) boule [26]. Infrared spectroscopy showed that the passivated surface has a dense layer of Si–H bonds, which effectively removes recombination-active dangling bonds. Truong *et al* demonstrated that hydrogenation of phosphorus-doped poly-Si layers significantly improved effective carrier lifetime (up to 4.75 ms). Hydrogenation was performed through SiN_x:H capping and forming gas annealing, resulting in V_{oc} up to 728 mV [27]. Advanced methods, including laser-assisted annealing and multilayer dielectric stacks (e.g., SiO₂/SiN_x:H, Al₂O₃/SiN_x:H) have improved hydrogen distribution and passivation uniformity [28]. Damm *et al* showed that hydrogenation of p-type poly-Si TOPCon on textured surfaces benefited from optimized dielectric stacks (e.g., SiN_x + AlOx) and high-temperature annealing (up to 700 °C), achieving low recombination current densities (as low as 7.9 fA cm⁻²) and τ_{eff} of 1.7 ms [29]. The study highlighted thermal activation kinetics and interface defect passivation to improve surface passivation and iV_{oc} (up to 726 mV). The Al₂O₃ capped layers substantially prevents the hydrogen effusion leading to 20–30 mV higher implied open-circuit voltage (iV_{oc}) configurations after firing. Effusion and FTIR analyses demonstrate that the sequencing of dielectric layers critically influences hydrogen retention, release kinetics, and bonding configurations up to the peak firing temperature (~ 800 °C) in Al₂O₃-capped silicon structures, thereby enhancing interfacial passivation [30].

Sopori *et al* systematically compared surface passivation schemes for minority carrier lifetime measurements in high-quality silicon wafers. By combining optimized wafer cleaning with passivation techniques such as thermal SiO₂ oxidation (1000 °C, 75 min) [31, 32], Al₂O₃, iodine–ethanol (I–E), and quinhydrone–methanol (QH–M), they achieved surface recombination velocities low enough to accurately measure bulk lifetimes exceeding 20 ms. Solid passivants like SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ offered stable, uniform interface quality and better carrier lifetime retention, particularly on high-resistivity wafers. Steinhäuser *et al* reported a record-effective minority carrier lifetimes of 0.18 s for p-type and 0.5 s for n-type in crystalline silicon [33]. This was done by combining high-quality surface passivation using TOPCon with hydrogenation through Al₂O₃:H/forming gas annealing. These methods improved interface quality with injection-independent surface recombination rates ($J_0s \approx 1\text{--}2$ fA cm⁻²). These improvements reduced surface and bulk recombination, leading to diffusion

lengths of about 2.5 cm. The results also confirmed defect passivation through hydrogenation and improved cleaning and gettering processes. Similarly, substantial advances in surface passivation—especially interface engineering through tuning of the SiO_x composition, optimization of hydrogenation dynamics, and integration of polycrystalline or amorphous passivating layers—have been essential for achieving high-quality passivation. These developments have enabled novel contact schemes such as tunnel oxide passivating contacts (TOPCon), silicon heterojunctions (SHJ), and dopant-free carrier-selective contacts (DF-CSC), which have delivered both higher effective minority carrier lifetimes and new record efficiencies for crystalline silicon solar cells [33–37].

Furthermore in recent times, industrial hydrogenation techniques including H-rich transparent conductive oxide (TCO) coating [38], remote hydrogen plasma treatment (RPHP) [39], or plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) of dielectric layers like hydrogenated silicon nitride ($\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$) [40–42], or Al_2O_3 [43] has become a standard practice. However, these commercial hydrogenation techniques face limitations such as thermal budget constraints, hydrogen-induced degradation under long-term operation (LeTID), and non-uniform passivation in complex architectures [44].

Additionally, high-temperature processes may not be compatible with certain types of wafers, i.e., float-zone (FZ) wafer. Elevated temperature exposure can lead to reactivation of latent defects (i.e., dislocation, stacking faults) or cause dangling bonds at the Si/ SiO_2 interface. In response to the identified challenges, we present a straightforward and economically viable hydrogenation method that ensures reliable and stable carrier lifetimes while maintaining a specific oxide thickness constraint. This study involves the passivation of silicon wafers by using an HF-etched wafer as a hydrogen-rich source, which is stacked with a chemically oxidized Si wafer under high-temperature conditions for a predetermined duration. Furthermore, we have optimised processing temperature to achieve the desired oxide thickness and enhance carrier lifetimes effectively.

Experimental

In this study, we used laser-cut 50 mm circular Czochralski M2 n-type Si wafers with a base resistivity of 2.25 Ωcm , a bulk lifetime of around 1 ms and a pyramidal textured surface with facet orientation of (1 1 1) from Longi Solar. The Si samples were processed in the automated wet bench for standard RCA (Radio Corporation of America) cleaning [45, 46], native oxide etching and wet chemical oxidation processes. RCA-cleaned samples are denoted as ‘Native’. Following RCA cleaning, the samples were subjected to native oxide etching using HF (48%) in a 1:10 ratio with DI-water (18.2 $\text{M}\Omega\text{cm}$) for 45 s and nitrogen dried for 20–25 s. The HF-etched wafers, further denoted as ‘Clean’, acted as a hydrogen-rich source when stacked with oxidized wafers during the hydrogenation process. Furthermore, some of these HF-etched samples are later subjected to wet chemical oxidation with nitric acid solution (HNO_3) at 100 °C for 30 min [47–50] and nitrogen (N_2) dried for 30–40 s. These samples are denoted as SiO_2 . For hydrogenation, these SiO_2 (chemically oxidized) wafers are consequently stacked with the prepared Clean (HF-etched) wafers, as schematically described in figure 2. These wafers stacks denoted as Clean| SiO_2 |Clean were thermally annealed in a pre-heated furnace at 650 °C for 15 min. After air-cooling in the fume hood, the carrier lifetime or thickness measurements are done. The delay between the annealing and measurement was 2 h. This so-called sandwiching process was repeated at different temperatures for investigating the trade-off between hydrogenation and oxidation, as higher temperatures lead to thermal oxidation dominating the hydrogenation process.

The experimental workflow implemented in this study, encompassing sample preparation, processing, and characterization steps, is delineated in the flow chart provided below in the figure 2(b).

The carrier lifetime is measured by the Sinton WCT-120 instrument, which uses the QSSPC method [51, 52] to determine the effective carrier lifetime τ_{eff} . The wafers with sufficiently high bulk lifetime are dominated by surface recombination, affecting the effective lifetime. This contribution of surface recombination is given by the surface recombination velocity S and wafer thickness W according to the equation $\tau_{\text{eff}} \cong W/2S$. After each processing step, including HF-etching, wet chemical oxidizing, and the Hydrogenation (sandwiching) process, the lifetime of the wafer with respect to time is noted to see how long the surface passivation lasts. This noted data gives us the time taken for each processed wafer to completely lose its surface passivation (here leading to loss of carrier lifetime).

To probe the bound state of Si-H on the surface, we employed the FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared) spectroscopy in the attenuated total reflectance (ATR) configuration [53]. We developed an insert, which was installed into the FTIR spectrometer (Vertex80, Bruker). The prisms used for this measurement have been fabricated from double-sided polished Si (1 1 1). These prisms were 260 μm thick with 0.8×1 cm dimensions. The excitation beam was introduced into the precisely polished prism at 45 degrees, passing through a sample through multiple reflections from the interface, gaining information on the surface-bound states and the presence of -H bonds after the sandwiching process. This measurement is used to determine the presence of the Si-

Figure 2. (a) Schematically explaining the stacking of HF etched and oxidized Si Wafers. (b) Flow chart summarizing the experimental workflow implemented in this study, including the main stages of sample preparation, processing, and characterization.

H bonds after sandwiching, indicating that the H atoms are diffusing into the Si/SiO₂ interface and forming a bond with the SiO₂.

Results and discussion

Before the detailed optimization was done, the concept of the sandwiching was tested by a control experiment. A control experiment, in which all conditions are kept identical except for the sandwiching stack under investigation, was performed. In this experiment, different sandwiching stacks were compared against a reference 'Clean|SiO₂|Clean' stack: namely Native|SiO₂|Native, Clean|Native|Clean, and Clean|Clean|Clean. The stacks Clean|Native|Clean, and Clean|Clean|Clean are used for the control experiment investigates the role of wet SiO₂, whether the sandwiching process itself is not overshadowing the role of wet SiO₂. The stack Native|SiO₂|Native investigates the role of hydrogen diffusion with respect to competing effect of thermal oxidation.

In general, the results indicate that the Clean|SiO₂|Clean stack renders chemically oxidized sample hydrogenated by enabling H atom to diffuse from the surface of etched wafer to SiO₂ layer at paired oxidized wafer (see figure 3). In particular, figure 3(a) shows that the Clean|SiO₂|Clean sample has a significantly enhanced passivation which indicates SiO₂/Si interface hydrogenation. This suggests that only for the Clean|SiO₂|Clean consequently a high flux of hydrogen species is established across interface when bringing wafers together, since none of the other control stacks supported comparable H diffusion or incorporation. Moreover, figure 3(b) shows that wafers processed with the configuration Clean|SiO₂|Clean keep the thickness of the oxide close to its

Figure 3. Testing the idea of sandwiching process ('Clean|SiO₂|Clean') against control experiments involving different stacks. (a) Carrier lifetime, (b) SiO₂ thickness performed at T = 650C.

Figure 4. (a) Dependence of carrier lifetime on annealing temperature and cumulative annealing time for stacked wafers. (b) Evolution of SiO₂ thickness as a function of annealing time at 650 °C.

initial value, in a range of about 2 nm. This indicates that hydrogenation occurs without inducing significant further oxidation of the silicon surface. However, for all other control samples the oxide thickness approximately doubled and therefore, to those samples, thermal oxidation dominated rather than hydrogenation under the same conditions. The simultaneous increase of the oxide thickness and lack of a relevant passivation enhancement means that in these control stacks the process is predominantly controlled by additional SiO₂ rather than by an effective H atom incorporation at the interface. Taken together, these findings emphasize the importance of stacking the Clean|SiO₂|Clean in enabling a full balancing of hydrogen transport and oxide stability for enhanced surface passivation.

To understand the temperature activation of hydrogen diffusion during the sandwiching process, an experiment with cumulatively (on the same sample) increased annealing temperature was conducted and the carrier lifetime of the wafers was measured, as shown in figure 4(a). The passivation, reflected in the carrier lifetime, increases gradually with both annealing temperature and time up to a certain thermal budget, beyond which a further prolongation of the annealing leads to a reduction in lifetime. This behaviour is consistent with the breaking of Si–H bonds above ~400 °C, which releases hydrogen atoms that diffuse into the Si/SiO₂ interface of the chemically oxidised sample when it is sandwiched between two etched wafers [54–57] as shown in figure 4(a). At temperatures above ~450 °C [58], however, thermal oxidation becomes increasingly significant, so that the beneficial effect of hydrogenation competes with and is eventually outweighed by additional oxide growth. To quantify this effect, we performed a complementary test at a fixed temperature of 650 °C, as shown in figure 4(b). For annealing times below 15 min, the oxide thickness remains at the desired value of approximately 2 nm, whereas for longer annealing times the thickness increases markedly beyond this range, indicating that thermal oxidation starts to dominate. The apparent increase in SiO₂ thickness after annealing is consistent

Figure 5. The variation of SiO₂ thickness is observed for (a) HNO₃, (b) H₂O oxidation with various temperatures when wafers are stacked together during sandwiching process.

Figure 6. Graphs illustrate the temperature optimization for (a) HNO₃, (b) H₂O oxidation during the sandwiching process with respect to carrier lifetime.

with thermally driven oxidation and oxygen diffusion under annealing conditions. Although TEM/XPS would provide direct confirmation of the oxide structure and interfacial chemistry, these analyses were not available in the present work; here we relied on the ellipsometry for thickness and FTIR-ATR for hydrogen-related bonding changes. Because the SiO₂ layer serves as a tunnelling oxide, thickness increases can reduce carrier tunnelling probability and increase contact resistivity, therefore we optimised the annealing process to 650 °C for 15 min to maintain the oxide thickness in the range of 1–2 nm. Correspondingly the maximum (τ_{eff}) obtained after wet oxidation and sandwiching process should be interpreted as the intermediate passivation stage. Higher effective lifetimes are typically achieved when the hydrogenated interface is combined with the passivation stacks like SiN_x:H and subsequent anneal to remove the recombination-active defects.

In the next step, the effect of the wet chemical oxidation route, i.e., HNO₃ or H₂O oxidation, was investigated on fresh samples for each condition, together with the influence of annealing temperature, as illustrated in figures 5(a), (b) and 6(a), (b). Figures 5(a) and (b) show the SiO₂ thickness as a function of annealing temperature for wafers oxidised in HNO₃ and H₂O, respectively, when stacked during the sandwiching process. For both oxidation routes, the oxide thickness remains close to the targeted value of ~2 nm at 650 °C, while at temperatures above 650 °C the thickness increases significantly and reaches \gtrsim 5 nm. Such thick oxides are not suitable for the intended passivation scheme and clearly indicate that, beyond 650 °C, thermal oxidation becomes dominant over hydrogen incorporation. Figures 6(a) and (b) present the corresponding carrier lifetimes as a function of annealing temperature for HNO₃- and H₂O-grown oxides, respectively, thereby focusing on the temperature dependence of the passivation. In both cases, the sandwiching process begins to be effective at 650 °C, where a pronounced increase in lifetime is observed, and the behaviour is almost identical for the two

oxidation routes. Considering the results from figure 4(a), we identify 650 °C as the optimal temperature window: at this temperature the oxide thickness remains low, while the carrier lifetime is maximised. At higher temperatures, no additional passivation benefit is obtained, whereas the oxide thickness increases to ≥ 5 nm according to figures 5(a), (b), confirming the onset of unwanted thermal oxidation. It is noted that at 650 °C the oxide thickness can be kept low and reproducible, with an experimental variation of $\pm 5\%$, which is acceptable for this type of thin passivation layer [59–62]. The combined analysis of figures 5 and 6 therefore demonstrates that both HNO_3 and H_2O oxidation, followed by sandwiching at 650 °C, provide a robust route to thin, hydrogen-rich oxides with enhanced carrier lifetime.

Figure 7 illustrates the lifetime stability of the sandwiched samples. The carrier lifetime remains relatively stable for an initial period of approximately 250 min, after which it gradually decreases to about 50% of its original value. This behaviour indicates that the hydrogenated SiO_2/Si interface is sufficiently stable over the timescale relevant for device processing, while a slow degradation of passivation sets in at longer times. The reduction in lifetime beyond 250 min can be attributed to an increase in surface recombination velocity, which is likely caused by gradual hydrogen out-diffusion and/or reconfiguration of interface defects that partially reverses the initial hydrogenation effect. Figure 8 shows the vibrational FTIR–ATR spectra of the samples after

each relevant process step, plotted with respect to a reference spectrum taken on the surface with native oxide after RCA cleaning. The band centred around 2100 cm^{-1} , labelled (1), corresponds to Si–H stretching vibrations on the bare silicon (1 1 1) surface. Because this surface is produced by wet processing rather than mechanical polishing, the band is broadened due to contributions from the fundamental Si–H mode at 2084 cm^{-1} [63], from coupled vibrational modes, and from Si–H₂ species [64]. After either oxidation or the sandwiching treatment, this band is completely removed, and new features appear at higher wavenumbers. These peaks, labelled (2)–(4) at approximately 2160 cm^{-1} , 2205 cm^{-1} and 2240 cm^{-1} , are assigned to Si–H₂(SiO), Si–H₂(O₂) and Si–H(SiO₂) bonding configurations, respectively [65, 66]. Note that in the spectrum recorded after HF treatment these oxide-related peaks (2)–(4) appear with negative intensity, which is consistent with using the native-oxide surface as the reference, since the native oxide already contains these vibrational modes. Because the FTIR–ATR spectra are obtained on an absolute scale, up to an additive constant, we assume for high-sensitivity analysis that after oxidation all direct Si–H bonds around 2100 cm^{-1} are eliminated so that the absorbance at this wavenumber is effectively zero. Under this assumption, the positive intensity of peaks (2)–(4) after wet oxidation indicates that the hydrogen content in the wet chemical oxide is higher than in the native oxide. Moreover, the further increase in the intensity of peaks (2), and especially (3), after the sandwiching process demonstrates that the sandwiching step introduces additional hydrogen into the oxide layer. This spectroscopic evidence is fully consistent with the enhanced electrical passivation observed in the carrier lifetime measurements.

Conclusion

We have demonstrated a facile hydrogenation technique called sandwiching for passivating silicon wafers. This method leverages thermal annealing in conjunction with a HF-etched wafer, as a source of hydrogen atoms, to enable the diffusion of atomic hydrogen into the silicon substrate. We tested that this technique reduced the dangling bonds and defects at the surface, resulting in an increased effective carrier lifetime measured by photoconductance method. Notably, by careful tuning of annealing temperature and time the competing thermal oxidation can be limited to keep the oxide thickness in the range of 1–2 nm, measured by ellipsometry. Using the combination of wet oxidation followed by sandwiching between HF-etched wafers and annealing at $650\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 min we achieved effective lifetime of 0.1 ms that is quite stable, retaining 50% of its original value for 250 min. Furthermore, the observed FTIR peak shifts confirm the incorporation of hydrogen atoms into the Si/SiO₂ interface, substantiating the efficacy of the sandwiching technique in hydrogenating the chemically oxidized silicon sample. Overall, this method holds promise for a simple laboratory method for reliable and stable hydrogenation of tunnel oxides on silicon wafers.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

Author contributions

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Conceptualization (equal), Data curation (lead), Formal analysis (equal), Funding acquisition (supporting), Investigation (lead), Methodology (equal), Project administration (lead), Supervision (equal), Validation (equal), Visualization (equal), Writing – original draft (lead), Writing – review & editing (lead)

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